

On the Joint Stiffness Design of 3D Printed Monolithic Fingers

Anjum Saeed^{1,*}, Mihai Dragusanu¹, Monica Malvezzi¹, Domenico Prattichizzo^{1,2} and Gionata Salvietti¹

Abstract—This paper introduces two novel approaches for adjusting the stiffness of robotic gripper joints, both offline and in real-time. The first method, called WaveJoints, is a passive design technique for task-specific 3D-printed soft-rigid grippers, where stiffness is predefined and adjusted through geometric parameters. The second method employs Twisted String Actuation (TSA) to achieve active real-time joint stiffness regulation, allowing robotic fingers to adapt dynamically to various manipulation tasks. Unlike the task-specific approach of WaveJoints, TSA provides versatile and spontaneous adaptation to the task. The combination of these methods enhances robotic manipulation across different environments by addressing both dynamic and static stiffness requirements.

Index Terms—grasping and manipulation, robotic grippers, additive manufacturing, twisted string actuators

I. INTRODUCTION

An ongoing problem in robotics is the development of hands and grippers that can efficiently manipulate objects in unstructured environments, regardless of their size, shape, or substance. Conventional robotic hands often use fully actuated systems and rigid links [1], [2]. Although this allows for accurate control of force, it is not adaptable to a wide range of possible scenarios. These limitations have led to the development of underactuated tendon-driven systems, which use compliant structures to passively adapt to object shapes and use fewer actuators [3], [4]. While these systems reduce mechanical design and control complexity, they lack joint stiffness control, restricting their capacity to execute sophisticated manipulation tasks. When finger movements and grabbing forces must be precisely controlled, this passive technique is insufficient.

Two separate strategies have been put forward to address these limitations and to make robotic fingers more versatile and useful through the introduction of ways to regulate joint stiffness [5], [6]. Developing a robotic finger that strikes a balance between simplicity, control, and adaptability is the fundamental challenge that both methods tackle.

The passive design method employs geometrical characteristics such as wave amplitude, length, and thickness to optimize the finger's design before manufacture. This method makes use of wave-shaped joints to offer adaptable stiffness.

We acknowledge the support of the European Union by the NextGeneration EU project ECS00000017 THE, Spoke 9 and by the Horizon Europe project HARIA (GA 101070292). The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors. The European Commission or its services cannot be held responsible for any use that maybe made of the information it contains.

¹ Department of Information Engineering and Mathematics, University of Siena, Siena, Italy

² Department of Humanoids and Human-Centered Mechatronics (HHCM), Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova, Italy

* Corresponding author email: a.saeed1@student.unisi.it

Fig. 1: The WaveJoints can change offline their stiffness. In a) the joint is used for the WaveGripper, a device for power grasp. In b) the joint is used for the Twist-WaveGripper, a gripper for in hand twisting of an object.

Fig. 2: The WaveJoints used for online change of stiffness. a) Assembly of the variable joint stiffness achieved through TSA. b) and c) fingertip trajectories for two different proximal joint stiffness levels: b) reference stiffness (TSA deactivated) and c) maximum stiffness (TSA activated).

These joints are a component of a 3D-printed construction that is monolithic, meaning that it combines rigid and flexible parts into one. The key novelty here is the capacity to alter the wave geometry during design to predefine the joint stiffness. Making use of this method optimizes production by carrying away with complicated control systems and extra actuators. The outcome is a soft-rigid gripper that is optimized for specialized activities like gripping things of different forms or twisting objects in the hand. Although this solution cannot modify stiffness in real-time, it does provide a very adaptable design that can be used for specialized tasks.

The second approach suggests a method of active control based on Twisted String Actuation (TSA). Through the use of a tendon-driven actuation system, TSA allows for the real-time change of joint stiffness using pre-compression. The main idea here is the dynamic stiffness control, which lets the robotic

finger vary its stiffness based on the job. The system can adjust to various gripping conditions by adjusting the flexural stiffness of the joints, giving it the precision and adaptability required to handle both fragile and rigid objects in real-time. The key benefit of this method is that it can dynamically alter the joint characteristics while operating, which increases the robotic finger’s adaptability for complicated jobs requiring manipulation of varying degrees of stiffness.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Offline Stiffness design

The approach here is to use wave-shaped joints to construct soft-rigid grippers of predetermined stiffness, all through a passive design process. Instead of actively adjusting stiffness during operation, geometric design parameters of the joints are determined during the design process, Fig. 1.

In this approach, the physical characteristics of the wave-shaped joints determine a pre-configured stiffness that the gripper can employ to carry out certain operations without requiring manual stiffness adjustment.

1) *Passive Stiffness Control*: Prior to manufacturing, the finger’s stiffness is fine-tuned by modifying the geometry of the wave-shaped joints, such as their length, amplitude, and number of ridges. The stiffness cannot be dynamically altered after manufacturing. The system’s joint stiffness is predetermined by the anticipated manipulation task and cannot be adjusted while in use, making it more task-specific.

2) *Design Simplicity*: This method has a more straightforward design since it is monolithic, meaning that each finger is 3D-printed as a single component. No extra actuators are needed to change the stiffness, making assembly and production easier. While manufacturing is simplified, the design does not allow for dynamic stiffness adjustment after printing the joints.

B. Online Stiffness Design

This approach to stiffness control makes use of a dynamic mechanism called Twisted String Actuation (TSA) to control the stiffness of the joints while they are operating. To make the robotic fingers more versatile in real-time, the TSA enables the stiffness to be dynamically modified according to the work needs, Fig. 2.

This approach focuses on actively regulating the stiffness of the joints to enhance the robotic finger’s performance and adaptability when manipulating objects.

Active Stiffness Control: By pre-compressing the joints with twisted strings, the TSA mechanism enables real-time change of the joint stiffness. This approach allows for a greater degree of flexibility and the modification of joint characteristics while the finger is in use. This system’s adaptability in stiffness adjustment makes it ideal for situations requiring varying manipulation forces or motions in real time.

Fig. 3: Grasp Experiment by using the WaveGripper with different objects. (a) Irregular box and (b) a soft toy. Twist rotation experiment with the Twist-WaveGripper. (c) Initial configuration. (d) Final configuration.

Design Complexity: The design becomes more complicated due to the need for extra motors and actuation systems (TSA) for adjusting stiffness with this method. Nevertheless, the flexibility it provides in real-time stiffness controlling is a benefit of this complexity.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Offline Stiffness Control

Two 3D-printed gripper prototypes were fabricated, each with a distinct purpose. WaveGripper, designed to power grasp various-sized objects, and Twist-WaveGripper, designed for in-hand rotation of cylindrical objects. A wide range of things were put to the WaveGripper’s test, including a plastic bottle, a cylindrical container, an empty rectangular box, a rigid irregularly shaped box Fig. 3a, and a soft puppet Fig. 3b, meanwhile the capacity of the Twist-WaveGripper to twist and turn a cylindrical item with a diameter of 60 mm was evaluated, as shown in Fig. 3c and Fig. 3d.

For the power grip test, the maximum and mean errors in the Euclidean distance between the theoretical and real trajectories of the fingertip were computed. The average mean error was 0.54 mm and the average maximum error was 1.74 mm. This shows that the gripper can precisely follow the desired motion, making it useful for gripping various objects.

In the same way, the trajectory tracking error was calculated for the twist finger in the in-hand object rotation task. The average mean error was 0.82 mm and the average maximum error was 3.71 mm.

B. Online Stiffness Control

A robotic finger was constructed, featuring three phalanges linked by flexible joints. A tendon drives finger closing, and the TSA controls joint stiffness. The TSA pulls the joint and

Fig. 4: Superposition of the cloud points obtained tracking the fingertip in the tests shown in Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c, during the finger flexion movement.

makes it stiffer by twisting threads that are attached to a motor. The string is compressed and the joint's flexural stiffness is altered as a result of the motor's rotations shortening it Fig. 2a.

A relationship between the force acting on the tendon and the finger's bending angle was determined. After applying different pre-compression levels, joint stiffness and finger movement were observed. All tests involved actuating the finger while adjusting TSA motor torque to create variable joint stiffness.

As seen in Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c, the bending angle decreases as the TSA is activated. The graphically represented link between pre-compression, applied force, and joint stiffness demonstrates how the TSA manipulates the robotic finger's behavior by actively controlling the stiffness of the joints.

As shown in Fig. 4, the fingertip trajectories during finger closure are affected by adjusting the joint stiffness. This demonstrates how the TSA influences finger motion and how adaptable it is for handling different objects using stiffness.

IV. CONCLUSION

Two strategies were presented that effectively address the difficulty of controlling stiffness in robotic grippers. By pre-defining stiffness through geometric design, the WaveJoints methodology provides a passive, task-specific solution that simplifies manufacturing while assuring precision for specified applications. On the other hand, the Twisted String Actuation (TSA) method is great for complicated and unpredictable manipulation tasks because it offers real-time adaptation, which lets robotic fingers change stiffness while being used. Combining these methods improves robotic manipulation by tackling pre-configured control and dynamic flexibility, which in turn increases the versatility of robotic grippers for various uses.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bicchi, "Hands for dexterous manipulation and robust grasping: A difficult road toward simplicity," *IEEE Transactions on robotics and automation*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 652–662, 2000.
- [2] D. Prattichizzo and J. C. Trinkle, "Grasping," *Springer handbook of robotics*, pp. 955–988, 2016.

- [3] G. Salvietti, I. Hussain, M. Malvezzi, and D. Prattichizzo, "Design of the passive joints of underactuated modular soft hands for fingertip trajectory tracking," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 2008–2015, 2017.
- [4] M. Malvezzi, Z. Iqbal, M. C. Valigi, M. Pozzi, D. Prattichizzo, and G. Salvietti, "Design of multiple wearable robotic extra fingers for human hand augmentation," *Robotics*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 102, 2019.
- [5] M. Dragusanu, G. M. Achilli, M. C. Valigi, D. Prattichizzo, M. Malvezzi, and G. Salvietti, "The wavejoints: a novel methodology to design soft-rigid grippers made by monolithic 3d printed fingers with adjustable joint stiffness," in *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 6173–6179.
- [6] M. Dragusanu, D. Troisi, D. Prattichizzo, and M. Malvezzi, "Compliant finger joint with controlled variable stiffness based on twisted strings actuation," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 7378–7384.